

SINGING SHEPHERDS, DISCORDANT DEVILS: Music and Song in Medieval Pastoral Plays

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Music features prominently in almost all medieval Shepherds' Plays, even if they are not musical dramas proper. This essay examines and compares the role of music, song, and dance in a series of biblical Shepherds' Plays from England, France, and the Iberian Peninsula. A comparative approach seems to be particularly appropriate in the case of late medieval drama, for, as Richardson argues, 'it allows us to distinguish what may be seen as variants on a universal given theme as the result of certain local conditions of place, associations, or tradition'.¹ The purpose of this work is to determine the main dramatic, narrative, and theological functions of musical elements in the aforementioned national traditions in order to ascertain their similarities and differences.

The dramas under analysis are fifteenth- and early sixteenth-century English, French, and Luso-Spanish Nativity plays in which shepherds feature as relevant characters.² These plays are: the Chester Painters' Play;³ the Towneley *First and Second Shepherds Plays*;⁴ the Coventry Shearmen and Tailors' Pageant;⁵ the York Chandlers' Play;⁶ Arnould Gréban's *Le Mystère de la Passion de Notre Sauveur Jésus-Christ*;⁷ Marguerite de Navarre's *Comédie de la Nativité de Jésus-Christ*;⁸ Fray Íñigo de Mendoza's *Coplas de Vita Christi*;⁹ Juan del Encina's *Égloga Representada en la Mesma Noche de Navidad*;¹⁰ Lucas Fernández's *Égloga o Farsa del Nacimiento de Nuestro Redemptor Jesucristo*,¹¹ and *Auto o Farsa del Nacimiento de Nuestro Señor Iesu Christo*;¹² and finally, Gil Vicente's *Auto Pastoril Castelhana*, *Auto dos Reis Magos*, and *Auto dos Quatro Tempos*.¹³

The unnamed, unnumbered, and undetermined shepherds of Luke's Gospel served as particularly useful tools in the hands of playwrights, who tried to turn them into representatives of mankind, thus enabling the audience to identify with them.¹⁴ There are several substantial differences between the English, French, and Luso-Spanish plays. To begin with, the Luso-Spanish works seem to be isolated pieces and, in addition, few of them have survived. This may point to the fact that the dramatic activity in Portugal and Castile was scarce during the Middle Ages. Actually, the majority of the playwrights included in this study keep up the medieval tradition of biblical drama, although their craft is closer to that of the

conversion undergone by a group of earthly, rustic, sinful shepherds who eventually become devout, redeemed Christians.

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NOTES

1. Christine Richardson 'The Medieval English and French Shepherds Plays' in *Festive Drama* edited Meg Twycross (Woodbridge: Brewer, 1996) 259.
2. Three of Gil Vicente's plays are included in this study. Vicente (1470–1536) wrote in Portuguese and Spanish, and even in a mixture of both languages. For a critical analysis of his work see *Gil Vicente: Clásico Luso-Español* edited M.J. Fernández García and Andrés José Pociña López (Mérida: Editorial Regional de Extremadura, 2004).
3. *The Chester Mystery Cycle* edited R.M Lumiansky and David Mills, 2 vols, *EETS* SS 3 (1974) and SS 9 (1986).
4. *The Towneley Plays* edited Martin Stevens and A.C. Cawley, 2 vols, *EETS* SS 13 and 14 (1994).
5. *The Coventry Corpus Christi Plays* edited Pamela King and Clifford Davidson (EDAM Monograph Series 27; Kalamazoo: Medieval Institute Publications, Western Michigan University, 2000).
6. *The York Plays* edited Richard Beadle (London: Arnold, 1982).
7. Arnoul Gréban *Le Mystère de la Passion* edited Gaston Paris and Gaston Raynaud (Paris: Vieweg, 1878; reprinted Geneva: Slatkine, 1970).
8. Marguerite de Navarre *Comédie de la Nativité de Jésus Christe* in *Les comédies bibliques / Marguerite de Navarre* edited Barbara Marczuk, Beata Skrzyszewska, and Piotr Tylus (Geneva: Droz, 2000).
9. Fray Íñigo de Mendoza *Coplas de 'Vita Christi'* (Madrid: Real Academia Española, 1953; facsimile edition of Zamora: Centenera, 1482) 1–153. Online edition in Biblioteca Virtual Cervantes (2002), collated with Fray Íñigo de Mendoza *Cancionero* edited Julio Rodríguez-Puértolas (Madrid: Espasa-Calpe, 1968) at:
<http://bib.cervantesvirtual.com/servlet/SirveObras/05810596599414995207857/p0000002.htm>.
10. Juan del Encina *Égloga Representada en la Mesma Noche de Navidad* in *Cancionero de las obras de Juan del Encina* introduction by Emilio Cotarelo y Mori (Madrid: Real Academia Española, 1928 reprinted 1989; facsimile edition of Salamanca: s.i., 1496) fols 104r–105v. Online edition in Biblioteca Virtual Cervantes (1999), collated with edition by Miguel Ángel Pérez Priego (Madrid, Cátedra, 1991) 107–116, and other editions. Online at:
<http://bib.cervantesvirtual.com/servlet/SirveObras/01159074653470455210035/p0000001.htm>.

11. Lucas Fernández's *Égloga o Farsa del Nacimiento de Nuestro Redemptor Jesucristo* in *Farsas y Églogas al Modo y Estilo Pastoril Castellano* edited Emilio Cotarelo y Mori (Madrid: Real Academia Española, 1929; facsimile edition of Salamanca: Lorenzo de Liom Dedei, 1514). Online edition in Biblioteca Virtual Cervantes: (2002), at: <http://bib.cervantesvirtual.com/servlet/SirveObras/01372731999137728644024/p0000003.htm>.
12. Lucas Fernández *Auto o Farsa del Nacimiento de Nuestro Señor Iesu Christo* in *Farsas y Églogas al Modo y Estilo Pastoril Castellano*: see above note 11 for details.
13. All three in Gil Vicente's *Auto Pastoril Castelhana* in *Compilaçam de todaslas obras de Gil Vicente* edited Maria Leonor Carvalhão Buescu, 2 vols (Lisbon: Imprensa Nacional-Casa da moneda, 1983).
14. The number of shepherds varies according to the different national traditions: three in the English plays, which may be related to the three Marys in the *Quem Quaeritis* or the subsequent *Visitatio Sepulchri*, though some scholars suggest that they may take after the three Magi present in the *Ordo Stellae*. In the Spanish and French plays, there are four. Also, in Spanish works, they are usually named after the Four Evangelists.
15. *Coplas de Vita Christi* by Fray Íñigo de Mendoza (1425–1507) does not show any pre-Renaissance features. It is not certain whether this long dramatic poem (ca. 1482) was ever enacted in front of an audience. For a discussion on the dramatic nature of this work, see Charlotte Sterne 'Fray Íñigo de Mendoza and Medieval Dramatic Ritual' in *Hispanic Review* 33 (July 1965) 197–245.
16. Juan del Encina is the author of secular pastoral plays whose titles include the term 'égloga' (eclogue), such as *Égloga de Cristino y Febea, Aucto del repelón, Égloga de Fileno, Zambardo y Cardonio, Égloga de las grandes lluvias, Égloga de Mingo, Gil y Pascuala, Égloga de Plácida y Vitoriano*. Lucas Fernández in his turn wrote a series secular and religious pastoral works which he collected in a volume significantly entitled *Farsas y Églogas al modo pastoril* ('Farces and Eclogues in the Pastoral Mode').
17. A stage direction in the *Comédia do Viúvo* indicates: *e foram-se as moças a el-Rei dom João III, sendo príncipe ... e ihle preguntaram dizendo* ('The maids approached King John the III, when he was still a prince, and asked him saying') (sd at 919). The text indicates that the prince (future king) actually answered them (sd at 925). See Carvalhão Buescu 1 438–9. See also R. Surtz *The Birth of a Theater: Dramatic Convention in the Spanish Theater from Juan del Encina to Lope de Vega* (Princeton & Madrid: Editorial Castilla, 1979) 9–13.
18. Patricia F. Cholokian & Rouben C. Cholokian *Marguerite de Navarre: Mother of the Renaissance* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2006) 180.

19. See Charles Mazouer 'Marguerite de Navarre et le mystère médiéval' *Renaissance and Reformation* 26: 4 (2002) 51.
20. See Luke 2: 8–22.
21. For an account of the origin and development of the *Officium Pastorum* and liturgical drama see, for instance, Karl Young *The Drama of the Medieval Church* 2 vols (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1962) 2 2–28; E. K. Chambers *The Medieval Stage* (Oxford UP, 1978) especially Book 3; Richard B. Donovan *The Liturgical Drama in Medieval Spain* (Toronto: Toronto Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies, 1958); *Teatro Medieval I: El Drama Litúrgico* edited Eva Castro (Barcelona: Crítica, 1997), and *Dramas Escolares Latinos: Siglos XII y XIII* edited Eva Castro (Madrid: Akal, 2001).
22. Joanna Dutka *Music in the English Mystery Plays* (Kalamazoo: Medieval Institute Publications, 1980) 6.
23. Strictly speaking, the shepherds are not Christian when the plays open because Jesus has not yet been born.
24. The only Spanish dramatic work in which the Angel appears is Fray Íñigo de Mendoza's *Vita Christi*.
25. See Peter Happé 'Farcical Elements in the English Mystery Cycles' in *Farce and Farcical Elements* edited Wim Hüsken and Konrad Schoell, with Leif Søndergaard (Ludus: Medieval and Early Renaissance Theatre and Drama 6: 1; Amsterdam: Rodopi, 2002) 29–43.
26. For a detailed study on the figure of the clownish shepherd in Spanish literature before Lope de Vega see John Brotherton *The 'Pastor Bobo' in the Spanish Theatre before the Time of Lope de Vega* (London: Tamesis, 1975).
27. All translations into English are by the author.
28. See *Égloga o Farsa* line 166, and *Auto o Farsa* lines 203–6.
29. One of the Tridentine prefaces to the Mass includes the formula: *Et ideo cum Angelis et Archangelis, cum Thronis et Dominationibus cumque omni militia caelestis exercitus himnum gloriae tuae canimus, sine fine dicentes ...* See *Missale Romanum* (Ratisbona: Congregation of Rights, 1921) 301.
30. According to Boethius (c. 480–c. 525) in *De institutione musica*, book 1; 2, the universe was divinely created and, as in the case of the consonant musical intervals, was founded on simple mathematical proportions. Due to its mathematical and acoustic properties, music became a mirror or *speculum* for divine order. See for instance Boethius *Sobre el fundamento de la Música: cinco libros* edited and translated Jesús Luque and others (Madrid: Gredos, 2009) 76–84.
31. See John Stevens 'Music in Mediaeval Drama' in *Proceedings of the Royal Musical Association* (1957–1958) 82. Stevens explains those musical items which were

- not governed by Boethian cosmology in terms of realism. However, Richard Rastall completely disagrees with this ‘realistic’ view since there are certain elements in the plays which are not realistic in a modern sense. For this discussion see Richard Rastall “Alle Hefne Makyth Melody” in *Aspects of Early English Drama* edited Paula Neuss (Cambridge: Brewer, 1985) 1–12. See also Richard Rastall essay ‘Music in the Cycle Plays’ in *Contexts for Early English Drama* edited Marianne G. Briscoe and John C. Coldewey (Indiana University Press, 1989) 192–218; and, by the same author, *Minstrels Playing: Music in Early English Religious Drama 2* (Cambridge: D.S. Brewer, 2001) especially chapters 1-4.
32. Women were not allowed to act in the Spanish theatre throughout the fifteenth and even the first half of the sixteenth centuries. In Puente Genil, a Spanish town near Córdoba, there is an annual parade of all New Testament male and female characters, but significantly, the only one not featuring in it is the Virgin Mary, since all personages are enacted exclusively by men. See Manuel Gómez Lara and others ‘Easter Processions in Puente Genil, Córdoba, Spain’ in *Medieval English Theatre* 9:2 (1987) 93–124.
 33. A Spanish and Portuguese type of folksong. According to an early-nineteenth-century English traveller, ‘The music ... was ... used in a species of dramatic interludes in the vulgar tongue, which were sung, not acted, at certain intervals of the service. These pieces had the name of *villancicos*, from *villano*, a clown, shepherds and shepherdesses being the interlocutors in these pastorals’; *OED* sv *villancico*.
 34. The process of changing from one hexachord to another (Oxford Music Online: <http://www.oxfordmusiconline.com>)
 35. A variation on *Versa est in luctum cithara mea* (Job 30: 30) from the Mass for the Dead.
 36. For this discussion see *Chester Mystery Cycle* edited Lumiansky and Mills, 2 110.
 37. Dutka in *Music in the English Mystery Plays* 11–13 points out that according to Satan and other devils, music is regarded as a mere din or noise in several English plays. For ‘sounds of Hell’ in English medieval plays see Richard Rastall *The Heaven Singing: Music in Early English Religious Drama 1* (Cambridge: D.S. Brewer, 1996) 199–215.
 38. For a discussion of *silete*, at first a musical calling for ‘silence’ (*Silete, silete, silentium habete*), but then developed into a musical interlude to cover gaps in the action, see the modernised version of Arnoul Gréban *Le Mystère de la Passion de Notre Sauveur Jésus-Christ* edited Micheline Combarieu du Grès and Jean Subrenat (Paris: Gallimard, 1987) 471; Peter Macardle *The St Gall Passion Play: Music and Performance* (Amsterdam: Rodopi, 2007) 165–72.
 39. See related note in *The Towneley Plays* edited Stevens and Cawley 2 501.

40. For an edition of the *Ordo Virtutum*, see *Nine Medieval Latin Plays* edited and translated Peter Dronke (Cambridge UP, 1994) 159–269.
41. For an analysis of music in *The Second Shepherds Play* see Dutka *Music in the English Mystery Plays*, especially 110–12, and Nan Cooke Carpenter ‘Music in the *Secunda Pastorum*’ in *Speculum* 26: 4 (October 1951) 696–700. See also Richard Rastall *Minstrels Playing: Music in Early English Religious Drama 2* (Cambridge: D.S, Brewer, 2001) 137–178.
42. See *The Towneley Plays* edited Stevens and Cawley 2 496, note 620. For a discussion of professional and amateur performers in the English plays, see Richard Rastall *The Heaven Singing: Music in Early Religious Drama 1* (Cambridge: D.S, Brewer, 1996) 300–368.
43. See *Oxford Music Dictionary* at <http://www.oxfordmusiconline.com>
44. See also *Oxford Music Dictionary* <http://www.oxfordmusiconline.com>
45. For an analysis of the non-religious songs contained in the English mystery plays see Dutka *Music in the English Mystery Plays* 65–81.
46. Definition by the *Spanish Royal Academy Dictionary*: <http://www.rae.es>.
47. The actual moment when the angel sings the *Gloria* is missing in the manuscript. This part must have contained the angel’s *Gloria* and his spoken message. See *The York Plays* edited Richard Beadle (London: Arnold, 1982) 130. In the late Middle Ages the significance of noise was ambiguous since it meant not only ‘din/noise’ but ‘A pleasant or melodious sound’; see *OED* sv *noise*.
48. A *breve* (breve) has one half or one third the time value of a *long*; Dutka *Music in the English Mystery Plays* 95–101.
49. See Cooke Carpenter ‘Music in the *Secunda Pastorum*’ 697.
50. The whole eclogue can be consulted online at: <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/verg.html>. For a Christian interpretation of the eclogue see for instance C.J. Metford *Dictionary of Christian Lore and Legend* (London: Thames and Hudson, 1983) 256. See also *The Oxford Dictionary of the Christian Church* edited F.L. Cross and E.A. Livingstone (Oxford University Press, 1974) 1444.
51. See Mayte Ridruejo and Rafael Portillo ‘La Traducción del Latín al Inglés en los “pageants” del “Ludus Coventriae”’ in *Translation Across Cultures: La traducción entre el mundo hispánico y anglosajón: Relaciones lingüísticas, culturales y literarias*. edited J.C. Santoyo (Actas XI Congreso AEDEAN; León: Universidad de León, Secretariado de Publicaciones, 1989) 153–8.
52. The actual words in the Vulgate are in the first case: *ego dormio et cor meum vigilat vox dilecti mei pulsantis aperi mihi soror mea amica mea columba mea immaculata mea quia caput meum plenum est rore et cincinni mei guttis noctium*

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(Canticum Canticorum 5: 2); and in the second: *quam pulchra es amica mea quam pulchra es oculi tui columbarum absque eo quod intrinsecus latet capilli tui sicut greges caprarum quae ascenderunt de monte Galaad* (Canticum Canticorum 4:3).

Text online at

http://www.vatican.va/archive/bible/nova_vulgata/documents/nova-vulgata_vetus-testamentum_lt.html.

53. Richard Rastall 'Alle Hefne Makyth Melody' 195. See above, note 33.